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Dated: August 07, 2020

Manuscript Acceptance letter

To,
Anthony Laurel*, Samuel Oak, Rex Kukui
(* Corresponding Author)

Manuscript Acknowledgement No: SJEEM-40-2020

Manuscript Title: First Confirmed Sightings of Apivenenum magnus
(Oak 1995) in Maui, Hawaii, U.S.A.

Dear Sir/Madam,

I take pride and pleasure to inform you that our reviewer has reviewed and recommended your Manuscript for publication in **Volume-7, Issue-8 (August, 2020)** in following Journal.

Journal Information

Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management (SJEEM)

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Article History

Article Received	Date of Acceptance	Proposed date of Publication
30/07/2020	07/08/2020	20/08/2020

Review Report

Category	Criteria
A	Strongly Recommended
B	Acceptable (as written with no need for any revisions)
C	Acceptable (with minor revisions/Editorial correction)
D	Ask for revisions and continue with a second review
E	Rejection (Do not accept for publication)

Final Decision: **Category B**